

Whether Government Digitalisation Reforms Promote Green Technology Innovation in Resource-Based City Firms

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Online Publication: 09 September 2025</p>	<p>A Government Digital Reform (GDR) is one of the important driving forces for resource-based city enterprises to carry out green technology innovation. This paper empirically examines the impact effect and mechanism of GDR on green technology innovation (FGI) of enterprises in resource-oriented cities using a sample of Chinese A-share listed companies in Shanghai and Shenzhen from 2011 to 2020. The findings are as follows: (1) GDR significantly promotes FGI in resource-based cities, and the effect is more significant in the central region and the third-tier cities; (2) GDR promotes FGI in resource-based cities by improving the degree of land resource mismatch (LRM); (3) there is a non-linear relationship between digital finance (DIF) and TOP10 on the main effect, specifically: for $DIF \leq 0.7916$, GDR does not significantly promote green technological innovation (FGI) in resource-based cities. GDR does not significantly promote resource-based city FGI, while when $DIF > 0.7916$, GDR significantly promotes FGI; when $Top10 \leq 0.3681$, the relationship between GDR and FGI is not significant, however, when $Top10 > 0.3681$, there is a significant positive relationship between GDR and resource-based city FGI. In summary, the findings of this paper not only reveal the important role of GDR in promoting FGI, but also delve into the internal mechanism and influencing factors of this role. This provides relevant policy makers with strong theoretical support and practical guidance, and helps promote resource-based city enterprises to achieve green, low-carbon and sustainable development in the era of digital economy.</p>
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<p>KEYWORDS: government digital reform, green technology innovation, digital economy, resource-based cities, threshold models</p>	

1. INTRODUCTION

With the increasing prominence of global climate change issues, resource-based urban enterprises are facing increasing environmental pressures (Carter et al., 2015). These firms are usually dominated by resource extraction and processing, consuming large amounts of natural resources and emitting waste, thus causing serious damage to the ecosystem (Haibin

& Zhenling, 2010). Green technology innovation is not only a way for these firms to survive in the face of increasingly stringent environmental regulations, but also a key to achieving sustainable production and economic growth (Luo et al., 2023). The adoption of green technologies can effectively reduce resource consumption and emissions, as well as provide companies with a competitive advantage to

meet the growing demand for green consumption. However, as shown in Figure 1, the level of green technology innovation

in resource-based cities is not high compared to non-resource-based cities.

Figure 1 Trends in green technology innovation by city

It is in this context that GDR has emerged, providing a great boost to the green technology innovation of enterprises in resource-oriented cities (Xie et al., 2023). As the regulator and guide of the whole economic system, the government's decisions and policies play a key role in the behavior of enterprises. Through digital reforms, governments can collect, process, and analyze data more efficiently and accurately to make more rational policy decisions (Newman et al., 2022). In addition, digital platforms can enhance information exchange and resource sharing between governments and businesses, and between businesses and enterprises, providing a broader space for cooperation and potential opportunities for green technological innovation (Oliveira et al., 2021; DiBella et al., 2023).

Green technological innovation focuses on the environmental benefits of corporate production, working to improve energy efficiency and reduce environmental damage (Dangelico & Pujari, 2010). It aims to promote high-quality growth in both the economy and the environment, and thus the impact factors in this area have attracted the attention of many scholars (Fu et al., 2023; Li et al., 2023; Liu & Feng, 2023). These studies typically examine both internal and external impact elements. Among them, external factors include institutional context and market conditions. Regarding the institutional context, some scholars have pointed out that appropriate institutional oppression can stimulate firms to increase their green technology innovation activities (Tu & Wu, 2021; Berrone et al., 2013), while there is also the view that the government's supportive strategy can encourage firms

to explore green growth pathways more proactively (de Abreu & Ceglia, 2018; DiBella et al., 2023). Droste et al. (2016) mentioned that government intervention may increase the overall innovativeness of the society. Huang et al.'s (2015) study found that regulatory oppression has a significant role in promoting green innovation. Meanwhile, Blackman et al. (2018) suggested enhancing regulatory intensity for better environmental outcomes. In terms of market influences, Doran et al. (2016) stated that both external regulation and customer oppression are key factors in motivating firms towards green innovation. Lin et al. (2020) found that external pressures such as shareholder lawsuits may place constraints on the innovative behavior of firm leaders, but when there are laws that limit such lawsuits, firms may increase their investment in R&D, which may lead to more technological patents. As for internal influences, Rodriguez and Wiengarten (2017) suggest that rational allocation of innovation resources is the key to enhancing green innovation capabilities. In contrast, Mao and Zhang (2018) and Tang (2015) argue that the decisions and attitudes of company executives have a significant impact on green innovation, especially when they have a deeper understanding of green technologies and assume greater social responsibility.

Despite the scarcity of research on the link between government digital transformation and green technology innovation, the existing literature generally agrees that the digital economy has a positive effect on firms' green technology innovation. Further, certain scholars have examined the drivers of the digital economy on innovation

and positive environmental externalities. Madhavan (1998) & Frishammar (2005), in their study, emphasized that the correct identification and assimilation of technological information is a core driver for firms to engage in production and product innovation. And the empirical study by Podrug et al. (2017) further corroborates this view. From the perspective of DIF, it seems to provide a solution to the mismatch problem that exists in the traditional financial system, effectively alleviating the financing difficulties of enterprises and further providing positive stimulus to their innovative activities (Li et al., 2023; Feng et al., 2022). Therefore, the digital economy has been gradually accepted by academics for promoting enterprises' green technological innovation, and has formed an organic combination with the deepening of digital reform (Zhang et al., 2022). However, so far, examining FGI from the perspective of government digital transformation is still an under-explored area. Based on this background, by analyzing empirical data from China during 2011-2020, this study attempts to reveal how government digital transformation affects resource-based firms' green technological innovation, and hopes to provide a new theoretical framework for research in related fields.

The contributions of this paper are as follows: first, geographic and city-size variability, this paper explores for the first time the impact of GDR on FGI from the perspectives of geography and city size, and finds that GDR is more significantly driven in the central region and the third-tier cities, which provides policymakers with targeted policy recommendations that greater digital reforms in these regions may lead to greater environmental benefits. Second, the perspective of resource allocation. This paper reveals that GDR promotes green technological innovation of resource-based city firms by optimizing land resource allocation, which provides a new perspective to understand how digital reform affects the real economy. Third, the mining of nonlinear relationships. By examining DIF and top ten shareholders' shareholdings, this study finds a nonlinear relationship between them and GDR's promotion of FGI. This implies that digital reforms may produce more significant effects under specific conditions, which provides a new research path for future studies. Fourth, the effect of equity structure: by introducing the variable of the shareholding ratio of the top ten shareholders, this paper provides us with a new perspective to understand how the equity structure affects the role of government policies on firms' innovation behavior. When equity is more concentrated, the government's digital

reforms may be more likely to affect firms' innovative behavior, which provides new insights into the study of corporate governance. Overall, this paper not only reveals how GDR promotes green technology innovation of resource-based city firms from multiple perspectives, but also provides useful insights for related theoretical research and policy formulation.

The paper is further structured as follows: in Section 2, we provide an in-depth discussion of the relationship and potential mechanisms between government digitization processes and FGI. Section 3 focuses on the modeling and data description, which details the definitions and sources of each relevant variable. In Part 4, we present and analyze the results of the empirical study, which provides a multifaceted view of how the government digitization process affects FGI. Part 5 explores the potential threshold effect of government digitization on green technology innovation. Part 6 provides specific policy recommendations for policymakers based on the findings and also points out the limitations of this study.

2. MECHANISMS AND ASSUMPTIONS

2.1 GDR and FGI in Resource-Based Cities

From the perspective of economics, information asymmetry is one of the main reasons for market failure. When information asymmetry exists, market participants are unable to make optimal decisions, which may lead to irrational allocation of resources and reduced market efficiency (Zhao et al., 2017). Through the government's digital reforms, the transparency of information has been improved, enabling market participants, especially firms in resource-based cities, to accurately assess the return on investment in green technologies (Sparrow & Makram, 2015). As a result, firms are more likely to invest in green technology projects with high returns. From a resource allocation perspective, effective resource allocation requires that capital, talent and other resources flow to their most valuable uses (Hollenbeck & Jamieson, 2015). With digital reforms, governments can more accurately identify industries and enterprises with green innovation potential and provide them with the necessary support accordingly (Wei et al., 2023). This will not only stimulate the development and application of green technologies, but also prevent resources from being wasted on projects with no potential. In addition, through digitalization, the Government can better monitor and assess the effectiveness of resource allocation and make timely policy adjustments to ensure the effective use of resources and

the continued promotion of green innovation.

GDR creates clearer and more transparent rules and metrics for resource-based urban enterprises from an incentive perspective. Economics emphasizes the symmetry of information and the influence of market participants' expectations on behavior. When governments adopt digital means to ensure fairness and transparency in the flow of information, firms are able to more accurately judge their own performance in terms of green technological innovations and the impact of such innovations on their position in the market. This clarity incentivizes firms to invest more in green technologies because they can clearly see the relationship between the return on investment and their green innovation efforts. From an interaction perspective, digital reforms in government reduce the costs associated with administrative inefficiencies(De Giovanni,2023). In economics, the role of the government is seen as that of a "night watchman", whose main duty is to maintain the order of the market and provide basic public services (Azam et al., 2023). As the government digitally improves its own efficiency, firms will need to spend much less time and resources interacting with the government, and will be able to focus more on their own green technological innovations. In addition, the digital reform also leads to closer cooperation between the government and enterprises and between enterprises, and this synergistic effect further promotes the sharing and dissemination of technology. In summary, the paper proposes the following hypothesis:

H1: GDR can promote FGI in resource-based cities.

2.2 Impact of GDR on the heterogeneity of FGI in resource-based cities

In analyzing the heterogeneous impact of GDR on FGI in resource cities, a key framework is to consider the comparative advantages, resource allocation, and information transfer mechanisms of different geographic regions. First, central regions and third-tier cities are located in the "middle zone" of China's economy. The comparative advantage of these regions lies in their rich natural resources. However, their integrated production capacity is limited by capital and technological constraints(Amir et al.,2023). In this environment, resource-based firms are likely to be highly dependent on government intervention and support, expecting government guidance to promote technological innovation. In contrast, the Eastern region, with its advanced capital markets and technological base, offers firms a wider range of channels for technological innovation, which includes support from the

private sector or other nongovernmental institutions. Thus, while GDR may provide additional information to firms in these regions, its incentive effect on technological innovation may be marginal. Further, western regions and fourth- and fifth-tier cities may be economically and technologically backward. While they face different challenges and needs than central and tier 3 cities, they also face environmental pressures and barriers to technological innovation(Feng et al.,2022). In these areas, while GDR can provide the necessary information and resources, the effectiveness of the reform may be limited due to their inherent barriers to technological innovation, such as infrastructure, education, and training. In summary, there is significant geographic heterogeneity in the impact of GDR on FGI in resource-based cities. This effect is more pronounced in central and third-tier cities, while it is relatively weaker in eastern, western and fourth and fifth-tier cities.

In addition, considering the role of heterogeneity in the digital economy, in terms of information asymmetry and the advantages of the digital economy, the core of the digital economy lies in the fast, low-cost flow and processing of information. Resource-based city firms often face information asymmetry in technological innovation-meaning that firms may not have enough information to assess the advantages of different technologies or determine the best R&D strategy(Xie et al.,2022). Government digital reforms can provide businesses with the latest information on research, policy incentives, and market trends related to green technologies through tools such as online platforms and digital databases. In regions with a highly developed digital economy, businesses themselves are more receptive to digital tools and solutions, and they are better able to leverage this information to guide technology R&D and innovation. Firms in such geographies are more likely to have the digital skills to quickly adapt and integrate information resources from the GDR, thereby accelerating the innovation process of green technologies. Considering the role of infrastructure in relation to the Broadband China strategy, effective information flow needs to be supported by a strong digital infrastructure. The government's Broadband China strategy intends to provide such infrastructure to ensure that information and data can flow quickly and without barriers everywhere(Rennings et al.,2022). For resource-based city businesses, this means faster access to and sharing of information on green technology innovations, collaboration with R&D partners, and even interaction with supply chain partners across the country

or even globally. In regions where the Broadband China strategy is being implemented, improved digital infrastructure means that businesses can more effectively capitalize on the advantages of the digital economy to further promote green technology innovation. To summarize, the heterogeneous impact of GDR on FGI in resource-based cities is more pronounced in regions with a high degree of digital economy development and the implementation of the Broadband China strategy. This is because firms in these places are more able to effectively address information asymmetry and utilize advanced digital infrastructure to accelerate the innovation process. In summary, this paper proposes the following hypothesis:

H2: The impact of GDR on FGI in resource-based cities is more significant in central and tier 3 cities.

H3: The impact of GDR on FGI in resource-based cities is more significant in cities with a higher degree of digital economy development and the implementation of broadband China strategy.

2.3 Mechanistic effects of LRM on GDR affecting FGI in resource-based cities

GDR can provide more transparent and efficient services to the public in many ways, especially in land management and allocation. From an economic point of view, resource mismatch is often caused by information asymmetry, delayed decision-making, or opaque resource allocation. GDR can reduce LRM in the following ways: first, it improves information transparency (Ansah et al., 2023). Through an online land management system, governments can publicize land use, ownership, and availability. This transparency can help potential land buyers and users make more informed decisions, thereby reducing resource misallocation. Second, reduce decision-making delays. A digitized approval process can reduce the time and complexity of land transactions. This means that resources can be allocated more quickly to those people or organizations that can use it most effectively (Banerjee et al., 2022). Third, optimize land allocation. By analyzing land use data, governments can better understand which areas or types of land are being used inefficiently. The government can then develop strategies to optimize land allocation, for example through incentives or redistribution strategies.

Land resources are the core assets of resource-based urban enterprises, and the efficiency of their use has a direct impact on their operational and innovation capabilities. The

mismatch of land resources can reduce green technological innovation in the following ways: first, capital liquidity constraints (Tewari et al., 2023). LRM may lead to a large amount of firms' capital being trapped in inefficient projects, thus limiting firms' investment in R&D and technological innovation. Second, it limits the space for innovation. In some cases, LRM may mean that firms do not have enough space to experiment or expand production. This may limit the firm's ability to experiment and innovate with new technologies or processes (Albitar et al., 2023). Finally, a deteriorated corporate image. Continuous LRM may lead to environmental problems such as over-exploitation of land and pollution. This may not only lead to legal risks for firms, but also damage their image, which may reduce their attractiveness in green technology cooperation and markets. In summary, LRM plays a key mediating role in the impact of GDR on FGI in resource-based cities. By optimizing the allocation of LRM, enterprises can invest more efficiently in green technology R&D and application. In summary, this paper proposes the following hypotheses:

H4: GDR promotes FGI in resource-based cities by reducing LRM and thus.

2.4 Threshold effect of DIF

In terms of incremental marginal benefits, the benefits of DIF may be limited in its infancy due to, among other things, fewer market players, immature technology and low consumer awareness of such financial services. However, as DIF develops, especially after reaching a certain threshold, its marginal benefits may increase rapidly. This means that DIF may not have a significant impact on FGI in resource-based cities in its early stages, but its positive effects may become particularly pronounced after it reaches a certain scale. In terms of network effects, like many digital products, DIF products and services benefit from network effects. When the number of DIF subscribers is small, the network effect may not be significant, but as the number of subscribers increases, the additional value that each new subscriber brings to existing subscribers is enhanced, thus significantly increasing the overall value of DIF (Chen et al., 2022). In terms of market depth and liquidity, when the DIF market is small, the market may lack sufficient depth and liquidity, which may lead to inefficient resource allocation. However, when the market reaches a certain size and depth, its liquidity is improved, and capital is able to flow more freely in the market, thus supporting green technology innovation more effectively. And

in terms of information asymmetry and trust, in the start-up stage of DIF, since the trust mechanism and information disclosure means are not yet perfect, information asymmetry may occur, leading to misallocation of resources. However, as the market matures, credit assessment, risk management and other important mechanisms can be improved, greatly reducing the information asymmetry in the market, thus enabling DIF to better serve the green technological innovation of resource-based city enterprises(Cheng & Torregrossa,2022). In summary, GDR has a nonlinear effect of DIF on FGI in resource-based cities. At the initial stage, due to various factors, its impact on green technology innovation may not be obvious; however, when it exceeds a certain critical point, with the gradual emergence of the various effects mentioned above, its impact may become very significant. Therefore, this paper makes the following assumptions:

H5: GDR has a threshold effect of DIF on FGI in resource-based cities.

2.4 Threshold effect of TOP10

The small percentage of ownership of the top 10 shareholders (TOP10) implies a relatively decentralized ownership structure of resource-based urban enterprises. In the early years of the GDR, this dispersed ownership may facilitate wider adoption and application of digital technologies. Individual shareholders are empowered to participate in decision-making and may bring different perspectives and resources to drive green technology innovation(Stein & Pentzold,2023). In addition, the information transparency and open data that may result from digital reforms are more likely to be accepted and utilized by these diverse stakeholders. Therefore, the positive impact of GDR on FGI in resource-based cities may be more significant when the TOP10 shareholding is small. Comparatively, when the TOP10 shareholding is large, the ownership structure becomes more concentrated, which may limit the speed and scope of resource-based city firms' response to GDR. Large shareholders may be more concerned with maintaining the status quo and protecting their interests than actively adopting new digital technologies or green technology innovations (Xiong,2023). While the GDR aims to promote transparency and innovation, when decision-making power is concentrated in the hands of a few large shareholders, they may resist innovations that may threaten their existing interests. Therefore, the impact of GDR on FGI in resource-based cities

may be less significant when TOP10 shareholdings are large. Based on the above derivation, this paper proposes the following hypothesis:

H6: There is a TOP10 threshold effect of GDR on FGI in resource-based cities.

3. MODEL CONSTRUCTION AND DATA DESCRIPTION

3.1. Modeling

Considering the estimation errors that may arise from inherent differences in industry and time, we use a dual fixed effects model for our study. The model, by introducing industry fixed effects, helps to control for the potential impact of unobservable industry characteristics on the study results, thereby reducing omitted variable bias and enhancing the robustness of the results. The specific model is constructed as follows:

$$GTI_{it} = \theta + \partial_1 GDR_{it} + \beta_i X_{it} + v_t + u_i + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

In the model, GTI_{it} represents the level of green innovation of listed companies in resource-based cities under different years as an explanatory variable. And GDR_{it} represents the degree of GDR, which is the key explanatory variable in our study. X_{it} A series of control variables are included. θ is a fixed intercept term, while ∂_1 represents the estimated coefficients of the core variables.

To further explore the mechanistic role of LRM, we constructed the following two models:

$$LRM_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 GDR_{i,t} + \sum Controls_{i,t} + Year + City + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (2)$$

$$GTI_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 LRM_{i,t} + \sum Controls_{i,t} + Year + City + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (3)$$

Where LRM is the mediating variable, model (2) is designed to explore the effect of GDR on LRM, while model (3) is designed to explore the effect of LRM on GTI.

In addition, in order to deeply explore the mechanism of DIF's influence on GTI in GDR, this study utilized a dynamic threshold regression model for analysis. The specific model is as follows:

$$GTI_{i,t} = u_i + GDR_{i,t} I(X \leq \gamma_1) A_1 + GDR_{i,t} I(\gamma_1 \leq X \leq \gamma_2) A_2 + Dig_{i,t} I(X_{i,t} \geq \gamma_2) A_3 + Bx_{it} + v_t + u_i + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (5)$$

In the formula, $I(-)$ represents the indicator function; the parameter $X_{i,t}$ characterize the threshold variables, DIF and TOP10, respectively; γ_1, γ_2 are the thresholds; A_1, A_2, A_3 and B denote the coefficients to be estimated by the model; and the other relevant variables have been described in the previous section.

3.2. Description of variables and data sources

3.2.1. explanatory variables

Firm Green Innovation (FGI): Within the framework of empirical analysis in economics, we have prioritized the use of actual data as the basis for our research, with relatively little use of subjective questionnaire results. Such empirical data provide us with a picture of how companies utilize their resources and what they get out of it. In the context of green technological innovation, the inputs of an enterprise are often in the form of capital and human resources for green R&D, and the corresponding outputs may be reflected in the accumulation of intangible assets, the number of green patents granted, and the economic benefits generated by new products. Given that the number of green patents granted more accurately reflects an enterprise's technological innovation strength and market recognition, as a patent needs to go through a rigorous review from application to granting, which ensures the quality and utility of the patent, this study therefore chooses the number of green patents granted (GTI2) as the evaluation index. Further, in order to explore how DIF differentially promotes green technological innovation, we consider green invention grants as substantive technological innovation (GTI21), while green utility model grants are categorized as strategic technological innovation (GTI22). Considering the "thick-tailed" distribution of the data and the many zero-value cases, we corrected the number of patent grants by adding 1 and transformed it into natural logarithmic form. In addition, in order to adapt to the time-lag characteristics of technological innovation, this paper selects the number of green patent applications as a proxy variable for robustness testing, and the proxy variables for the number of green patent grants, substantive technological innovation, and strategic technological innovation are denoted as GTI1, GTI11, and GTI12, respectively.

3.2.2. Explanatory variables

Government Digital Reform (GDR): from a policy economics perspective, government adoption of digital transformation is extremely critical. By analyzing government work reports in depth, especially by applying text mining methods, we can capture the government's attitude and concern towards digital economic transformation. These reports not only represent the government's strategic direction, but also provide us with a means to verify the reliability of the data. To quantify this concern, we compiled a thesaurus of keywords related to digitalization. In this study, we collected government work reports from 2001 to 2020 and counted the

digitization-related keywords in them, aiming to reveal the government's digital economy concern. Specifically, we summarize the frequency of keyword appearances in each year for each city and calculate its percentage in the overall report. This data can show us the level of governmental attention to digital topics. Inspired by Liu et al. (2023), we selected 121 keywords, which can be broadly categorized into "digital tools" (e.g., big data, blockchain, etc.) and "digital practices" (e.g., digitization of the service industry, e-government, etc.). Based on this categorization, we used the frequency ratio of the two keywords in the report as a proxy variable to measure the digitization process of the government, in which "digital tools" and "digital practices" are labeled as DT and DA. By summing up these two indicators, we form a composite indicator, i.e. Government Digital Development Index GDR.

3.2.3. Remaining variables

1. Mechanism variables

Land Resource Mismatch (LRM): from the microfoundations of economics and mechanism design theory, we explore in depth the possible mediating role of land resource allocation on the relationship between GDR and FGI. In this regard, the study by Li et al. (2016) provides a valuable frame of reference. Specifically, they propose a succinct yet insightful measure, the LRM, by comparing the difference between the area of land granted by agreement and the area actually granted. Inheriting and developing the methodology of Li et al. we argue that this ratio not only reflects the efficiency of the allocation of land resources, but also reveals a new perspective on the interaction between market mechanism and government behavior. This interaction may have implications for the government's digitization strategy and its promotion of enterprises toward green technology innovation.

2. Threshold variables

Digital Finance (DIF): In this paper, in the field of DIF measurement, although there are certain limitations in the early index system, the Beida Digital Inclusive Finance Index has gradually become the leading standard in the field by virtue of its comprehensiveness and scientific nature, and has been widely adopted by economics researchers. This study chooses to refer to the 2011-2020 digital inclusive finance index at the prefecture and city level published by the Financial Research Center as the main measurement tool. This index is deeply segmented and includes three dimensions: breadth of coverage, depth of use, and quality of digital services. Specifically, breadth of coverage focuses on the

popularity of financial services, represented by account coverage; depth of use uses specific financial business data to reflect the application of DIF services in actual scenarios; and quality of digital services pays more attention to their usefulness and convenience for users. In order to ensure the comprehensiveness of the study, this study adopts the overall Digital Inclusive Finance Index (DIF) as the measurement index. Before conducting the empirical analysis, we standardized this data, aiming to guarantee the robustness and comparability of the research results.

Proportion of Top 10 Shareholders (TOP10): TOP10 (TOP10) is an important corporate governance indicator that reflects the degree of concentration of a company's equity. When the proportion of shares held by the top ten shareholders to the total shares of the company is high, it indicates that the company's shareholding is more concentrated, which may have an impact on the company's business decisions, strategic direction, and risk appetite. From a theoretical perspective, companies with highly concentrated shareholdings, especially those with a high percentage of shares held by the top ten shareholders, tend to be more susceptible to the influence of large shareholders. Such firms may focus more on the interests of large shareholders and less on the interests of small shareholders in their decision-making. This may lead to more conservative or risky decisions by the company, depending on the risk appetite of the majority shareholder. In addition, the TOP10 is also a window into a company's internal control and monitoring mechanisms. When equity is highly concentrated, a company's internal control mechanisms may be less stringent, as large shareholders may have more ability and incentive to monitor the company's management. However, this may also lead to company decisions relying too much on the wishes of a small number of large shareholders and ignoring the opinions and suggestions of other stakeholders. Overall, the Top 10 (TOP10) is a key indicator that can reveal a company's shareholding structure, internal governance mechanisms, and decision-making preferences, which may have far-reaching impacts on the company's business strategies and performance. When conducting business analysis and research, this indicator is often used as a threshold variable to examine its potential impact on other economic variables.

3. Control variables

To ensure the completeness of the model and prevent the omission of key variables, this study incorporates the following control variables as suggested by Pan et al. (2023) and Li et al. (2022): the size of the firm (Size), the composition of capital (Lev), the return on assets (ROA), the firm's potential for growth (Growth), the ratio of the top ten shareholdings (Top10), the Tobin Q index (TobinQ), ownership pattern (SOE), and Big 4 auditor's audit (Big4). To further enhance the accuracy of the model, we also include year and industry fixed effects and choose robust standard errors as estimators.

3.3 Data sources and descriptive statistics of variables

Based on the results of the descriptive statistics in Table 1, we find that the average value of the overall green technology innovation (GTI2) of resource-based urban enterprises is 0.237, which means that the number of authorized green technology innovations is relatively low among all resource-based urban enterprises. However, its maximum value reaches 2.485, indicating that there are still some resource-based city enterprises that are doing particularly well in this area. The comparison between substantive technology innovation (GTI21) and strategic technology innovation (GTI22) shows that resource-based city firms invest more in strategic technology innovation, while substantive technology innovation is relatively low. Regarding GDR, the mean value is 0.185, which implies that there are some differences in the level of governmental attention to digitization in different cities. The maximum value is 0.559, which indicates that governments in certain regions pay great attention to digitization. Based on the descriptive statistics, we can draw the following preliminary conclusions: first, green technology innovation has not yet been widely promoted among the surveyed enterprises, but a few of them do do a good job in this area. Second, enterprises are more inclined to carry out strategic technological innovation rather than substantive technological innovation. Third, the level of government attention to digitization varies from region to region, with governments in certain regions attaching great importance to it.

Table1 Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max.
<i>GTI21</i>	0.0801	0.275	0	1.609
<i>GTI22</i>	0.178	0.434	0	2.303
<i>GTI2</i>	0.237	0.505	0	2.485
<i>DA</i>	0.118	0.0871	0	0.419
<i>DT</i>	0.0672	0.0654	0	0.272
<i>GDR</i>	0.185	0.127	0	0.559
<i>Size</i>	22.22	1.278	19.98	25.54
<i>Lev</i>	0.430	0.205	0.0503	0.942
<i>ROA</i>	0.0410	0.0652	-0.218	0.241
<i>Growth</i>	0.156	0.425	-0.554	2.783
<i>Top10</i>	0.574	0.154	0.233	0.880
<i>TobinQ</i>	1.896	1.280	0	8.321
<i>SOE</i>	0.406	0.491	0	1
<i>Big4</i>	0.0372	0.189	0	1

4. EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

4.1. Baseline regression results and discussion

According to the above regression results, GDR is positively correlated with FGI, especially in the models of GTI2, GTI21, and GTI22, where the coefficients of GDR are significantly and positively influenced at 1% or 5% level. This implies that GDR may help to promote FGI in resource-based cities. In particular, when we consider digital practices (DA) and digital tools (DT) separately, both show a significant positive relationship on GTI2, GTI21, and especially the coefficients of digital tools (DT) are relatively large, implying that they may play a more critical role in promoting green

technology innovation. However, the effect of DA on GTI22 is not significant, suggesting that DA may not be able to promote strategic technological innovation of resource-based urban firms. Meanwhile, firm size (Size) showed a significant positive effect in all models, suggesting that large firms in resource-based cities are more likely to engage in green technology innovation. On the other hand, Growth potential (GDR) is negatively related to green technology innovation, probably because fast-growing firms focus more on scale expansion than technology innovation in the short term. Overall, GDR has a positive contribution to FGI, especially through the promotion and application of digital tools.

Table 2. Benchmark regression results

VARIABLE	<i>GTI2(1)</i>	<i>GTI21(2)</i>	<i>GTI22(3)</i>	<i>GTI2(4)</i>	<i>GTI21(5)</i>	<i>GTI22(6)</i>	<i>GTI2(7)</i>	<i>GTI21(8)</i>	<i>GTI22(9)</i>
<i>GDR</i>	0.2794*** (2.6194)	0.1609** (2.5055)	0.1998** (2.1801)						
<i>DA</i>				0.2506* (1.7590)	0.1451* (1.6637)	0.1629 (1.3302)			
<i>DT</i>							0.4903** (2.3742)	0.2761** (2.2547)	0.3805** (2.1403)
<i>Size</i>	0.1109*** (7.8418)	0.0452*** (5.8276)	0.0880*** (6.8585)	0.1105*** (7.8104)	0.0450*** (5.8017)	0.0877*** (6.8331)	0.1111*** (7.8352)	0.0453*** (5.8251)	0.0882*** (6.8648)
<i>Lev</i>	-0.0640 (-0.9460)	-0.0629 (-1.5131)	-0.0554 (-0.9777)	-0.0620 (-0.9095)	-0.0618 (-1.4710)	-0.0543 (-0.9531)	-0.0722 (-1.0671)	-0.0676 (-1.6220)	-0.0616 (-1.0872)
<i>ROA</i>	0.2128 (1.1389)	0.0123 (0.1118)	0.1944 (1.1925)	0.2067 (1.1033)	0.0088 (0.0800)	0.1892 (1.1597)	0.2005 (1.0734)	0.0051 (0.0467)	0.1860 (1.1411)

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<i>Growth</i>	-0.0701** *	-0.0196*	-0.0605** *	-0.0705** *	-0.0199*	-0.0607** *	-0.0691** *	-0.0190	-0.0597** *
	(-3.7822)	(-1.6913)	(-3.6678)	(-3.8024)	(-1.7085)	(-3.6796)	(-3.6771)	(-1.6318)	(-3.5833)
<i>Top10</i>	-0.0817	-0.0325	-0.0523	-0.0771	-0.0299	-0.0488	-0.0810	-0.0320	-0.0524
	(-1.0595)	(-0.7814)	(-0.7570)	(-1.0028)	(-0.7175)	(-0.7091)	(-1.0502)	(-0.7719)	(-0.7550)
<i>TobinQ</i>	-0.0110	-0.0023	-0.0092	-0.0112	-0.0024	-0.0093	-0.0113	-0.0024	-0.0093
	(-1.4260)	(-0.5305)	(-1.3941)	(-1.4479)	(-0.5543)	(-1.4148)	(-1.4587)	(-0.5605)	(-1.4209)
<i>SOE</i>	0.0886***	0.0288*	0.0782***	0.0906***	0.0299**	0.0797***	0.0893***	0.0292**	0.0784***
	(3.6140)	(1.9609)	(3.7870)	(3.6977)	(2.0374)	(3.8622)	(3.6460)	(1.9999)	(3.8003)
<i>Big4</i>	0.2826***	0.1989***	0.1637**	0.2863***	0.2010***	0.1661**	0.2757***	0.1950***	0.1583**
	(3.0538)	(3.1705)	(2.1183)	(3.0886)	(3.2031)	(2.1418)	(2.9816)	(3.1040)	(2.0559)
<i>Year effect</i>	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
<i>Industry effect</i>	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
<i>Constant</i>	-2.2272** *	-0.9196** *	-1.7791** *	-2.2004** *	-0.9043** *	-1.7579** *	-2.2082** *	-0.9082** *	-1.7680** *
	(-7.3150)	(-5.4847)	(-6.4394)	(-7.2260)	(-5.4027)	(-6.3581)	(-7.2363)	(-5.4275)	(-6.3907)
<i>Observations</i>	2,230	2,230	2,230	2,230	2,230	2,230	2,230	2,230	2,230
<i>R-squared</i>	0.2134	0.1403	0.1863	0.2118	0.1386	0.1850	0.2132	0.1400	0.1864

4.2. robustness and endogeneity tests

4.2.1 Robustness Tests

After replacing the dependent variable, the positive correlation between GDR (GDR) and FGI (GTI1), as well as its two sub-dimensions, GTI11 (Substantial Technological Innovation) and GTI12 (Strategic Technological Innovation), is still significant, and both of them reach the 1% level of significance. This suggests that the government's digitalization efforts have a positive impact on green technological innovations of firms in resource-based cities, as measured by both the number of licenses and applications. The impact of the application of digitization tools (DA) on GTI1 and its two sub-dimensions is significant at the 1% significant level, indicating that the use of digitization tools has a clear

contribution to green technology innovation. Regarding digital technology (DT) and green technology innovation, similarly to before, the positive correlation of DT with GTI1, GTI11, and GTI12 are all significant at the 1% significant level, highlighting the central role of digital technology in promoting green technology innovation. Taken together, these robustness test results further confirm that GDR, the application of digitization tools, and digitization technologies have a clear positive impact on FGI in resource-based cities, both in terms of the number of applications and licenses. At the same time, these findings enhance our confidence in the original model and show the consistency of its predictions across different metrics.

Table 3. Robustness test results

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
VARIABLES	GTI1	GTI11	GTI12	GTI1	GTI11	GTI12	GTI1	GTI11	GTI12
<i>GDR</i>	0.5174*** (3.8618)	0.3578*** (3.6602)	0.3653*** (3.5621)						
<i>DA</i>				0.4942*** (2.6619)	0.4121*** (2.9667)	0.2966** (2.1480)			
<i>DT</i>							0.8692*** (3.4198)	0.4986*** (2.7417)	0.6943*** (3.5566)

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<i>control variable</i>	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
<i>Year effect</i>	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
<i>Industry effect</i>	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
<i>Constant</i>	-2.7448** *	-2.0580** *	-1.7589** *	-2.6991** *	-2.0355** *	-1.7199** *	-2.7064** *	-2.0232** *	-1.7384** *
	(-7.3484)	(-7.3102)	(-6.2552)	(-7.2209)	(-7.2264)	(-6.1109)	(-7.2352)	(-7.1832)	(-6.1690)
<i>Observations</i>	2,230	2,230	2,230	2,230	2,230	2,230	2,230	2,230	2,230
<i>R-squared</i>	0.2380	0.2282	0.1879	0.2350	0.2265	0.1842	0.2371	0.2261	0.1883

4.2.2 Endogeneity test

In order to address the potential endogeneity issue more precisely, the instrumental variable approach is chosen as a strategy in this study. In particular, considering that the innovation behavior of resource-based urban firms may be affected by prior period GDR (GDR), we use 1-period lagged GDR (L.GDR) as an instrumental variable for current GDR. The idea of this approach is based on the notion that historical policy changes may affect firms' current strategies and behaviors, but do not directly affect firms' current-period green technology innovations. Therefore, the use of lagged GDR can help us obtain a clearer and more accurate estimate of the effect of GDR on FGI by providing us with an instrumental variable that is uncorrelated with the potential disturbance factor but correlated with current GDR (Wooldridge, 2002). This approach aims to eliminate the bias

caused by potential omitted variables and provide us with a more reliable estimate.

The results show that the lagged one-period values of both GDR (GDR) and digitization technology (DT) have a significant positive relationship with their present values and have a significant positive impact on FGI (GTI2), although the degree of significance varies. In contrast, although the lagged one-period value of the application of digitalization tools (DA) has a significant positive relationship with its present value, it does not have a significant effect on GTI2. These results not only validate the reliability of the instrumental variable strategy, but also highlight the fact that the mere application of digital tools may not be sufficient in driving technological innovation, whereas deep technological convergence and strategic governmental digital reforms may play a more catalytic role.

Table 4. Endogeneity test results

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
VARIABLES	GDR	GTI2	DA	GTI2	DT	GTI2
<i>L. GDR</i>	0.3361*** (12.6137)					
<i>GDR</i>		0.6686* (1.9393)				
<i>L. DA</i>			0.2885*** (10.0873)			
<i>DA</i>				0.5971 (1.0821)		
<i>L. DT</i>					0.3617*** (12.6560)	
<i>DT</i>						1.2423** (2.0637)
<i>control variable</i>	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
<i>Year effect</i>	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y

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<i>Industry effect</i>	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
<i>Constant</i>	0.1886*** (2.8388)		0.1072** (2.3638)		0.0843** (2.2287)	
<i>Observations</i>	1,781	1,781	1,781	1,781	1,781	1,781
<i>R-squared</i>	0.4602	0.0858	0.3936	0.0883	0.4543	0.0835

4.3 Heterogeneity analysis

The analysis of the benchmark model shows that regional GDR significantly advances FGI in resource-based cities, and this finding remains robust after various robustness and endogeneity tests. To gain a deeper understanding of how GDR affects green technology innovation in different urban contexts and stages of digital economy development, this study further categorizes and analyzes the sample.

4.2.1 Urban heterogeneity

When we consider urban heterogeneity, it is clear that the effect of GDR (GDR) on FGI (GTI2) in resource-based cities varies across city location and size. In the dimension of city location, the effect of GDR on FGI is positive but not significant in eastern resource-based cities. This may indicate that the direct contribution of GDR to innovation may be weaker in the more economically developed eastern part of the country. On the contrary, central resource-based cities show a positive and significant relationship between GDR and

FGI, which implies that digital reforms may have brought more innovation opportunities for firms in these relatively less developed regions. However, resource-based cities in the West do not show any significant relationship, which may imply that other factors such as infrastructure or education may be more critical in these areas. From a city size perspective, there is a positive and significant relationship between GDR and FGI in Tier 3 resource-based cities, which further emphasizes the importance of digital reforms in these medium-sized cities. In contrast, the relationship is not significant in Tier 4 resource cities, while in Tier 5 resource cities, the certainty of this result may be challenged due to the small sample of observations, despite the large coefficient value. In summary, we can see that the economic status and size of cities play a key role in the impact of GDR on FGI. These differences may be related to factors such as the economic structure of the cities, government policies, and the degree of digitization, and deserve to be further explored in future studies.

Table 5. Results of the urban heterogeneity analysis

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	city location			city scale		
	the east	central section	western part	third-tier city	fourth-tier city	fifth-tier city
VARIABLES	GTI2	GTI2	GTI2	GTI2	GTI2	GTI2
<i>GDR</i>	0.3068 (1.5371)	0.3513** (2.0137)	-0.0166 (-0.0731)	0.2900* (1.8712)	0.0671 (0.4599)	0.6504 (1.1422)
<i>control variable</i>	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
<i>Year effect</i>	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
<i>Industry effect</i>	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
<i>Constant</i>	-2.2924*** (-4.3179)	-2.5816*** (-4.2383)	-0.9108 (-1.2906)	-3.0545*** (-7.1559)	-0.9884** (-2.4222)	-0.0933 (-0.0877)
<i>Observations</i>	889	752	374	1,275	869	82
<i>R-squared</i>	0.2778	0.3231	0.2147	0.3359	0.1693	0.5245

4.2.2 Digital economy heterogeneity

Based on the heterogeneity of the digital economy, we conducted further analysis. The level of digital economy can be categorized as low and high, while we also consider the presence or absence of the Broadband China strategy. First,

for resource-based regions with a low level of digital economy, the effect of GDR (GDR) on firms' green technology innovation (GTI2) is positive, but its t-value is 1.6176, implying that this effect is not at any conventional level of significance. In contrast, the impact of GDR is significant and

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at the 5% significant level in resource-based regions with a higher level of digital economy, with a coefficient of 0.3185 and a t-value of 1.9727. This suggests that GDR has a more significant effect on the advancement of green technological innovations in more digitally mature regions. Considering the broadband China strategy, the effect of GDR on GTI2 is positive but not significant in regions where the strategy is not implemented, with a coefficient of 0.1543 and a t-value of 1.1608. However, in regions where the broadband China strategy is implemented, the promotion of GTI2 by GDR is

significantly stronger, with a coefficient of 0.6259 and, at the 1% significant level, a t-value of 3.1857. This means that the positive impact of GDR on FGI in resource-based cities is more obvious when the region deeply implements the broadband China strategy. Taken together, these results reveal the important role of digital economy heterogeneity in the impact of GDR on green technology innovation. Especially in regions with more developed digital economies or implemented broadband strategies, GDR is more likely to promote green technology innovation.

Table 6. Results of the analysis of the heterogeneity of the digital economy

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	Level of the digital economy		Broadband China Strategy	
	lower head)	(one's your (honorific)	NO	YES
VARIABLES	GTI2	GTI2	GTI2	GTI2
<i>GDR</i>	0.2212 (1.6176)	0.3185** (1.9727)	0.1543 (1.1608)	0.6259*** (3.1857)
<i>control variable</i>	Y	Y	Y	Y
<i>Year effect</i>	Y	Y	Y	Y
<i>Industry effect</i>	Y	Y	Y	Y
<i>Constant</i>	-2.0389*** (-4.4954)	-2.5456*** (-5.6079)	-2.1281*** (-5.7055)	-2.5365*** (-4.3314)
<i>Observations</i>	1,115	1,111	1,577	651
<i>R-squared</i>	0.2563	0.2736	0.2032	0.2770

5. FURTHER ANALYSIS

5.1 Mediating effects of LRM

From the regression results provided in Table 7, we can observe the effects of GDR, DA and DT on LRM and LRM on GTI2. We can analyze the following aspects to explore the mediating effect of LRM: First, GDR has a significant negative effect on LRM with a coefficient of -0.0883 and at the 5% significant level. This implies that GDR may lead to a better allocation of land resources or reduce the mismatch of land resources. Secondly, DA has a significant negative effect on LRM with a coefficient of -0.0871 and at 10% significant level. This implies that the application of digitization tools may have a positive effect on the allocation of land resources, thus reducing mismatch. Thirdly, DT has a significant negative effect on LRM with a coefficient of -0.1450 and at

the 5% significant level (t-value of -2.2330). This also suggests that the introduction of digital technology may contribute to the allocation of LRM. Fourth, the negative effect of LRM on GTI2 is significant in all three models with a coefficient of -0.1418 and at the 1% significant level (t-value of -2.6023). This implies that an increase in LRM may reduce the green technology innovation of resource-based urban enterprises. In a comprehensive analysis, GDR, DA and DT all indirectly promote green technology innovation by reducing LRM. Among them, GDR, the application of digital tools and the introduction of digital technology all have the effect of reducing LRM, while the increase of LRM adversely affects green technology innovation. Therefore, LRM plays a mediating role in this.

Regression results for the mediating role of LRM

VARIABLES	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	LRM	GTI2	LRM	GTI2	LRM	GTI2
<i>GDR</i>	-0.0883** (-2.4901)					
<i>DA</i>			-0.0871* (-1.6720)			
<i>DT</i>					-0.1450** (-2.2330)	
<i>LRM</i>		-0.1418*** (-2.6023)		-0.1418*** (-2.6023)		-0.1418*** (-2.6023)
<i>control variable</i>	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
<i>Year effect</i>	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
<i>Industry effect</i>	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
<i>Constant</i>	0.6723*** (6.6399)	-2.0756*** (-6.8047)	0.6649*** (6.5649)	-2.0756*** (-6.8047)	0.6655*** (6.5769)	-2.0756*** (-6.8047)
<i>Observations</i>	2,230	2,230	2,230	2,230	2,230	2,230
<i>R-squared</i>	0.1551	0.2129	0.1541	0.2129	0.1547	0.2129

5.2 Threshold effect of DIF

Table 7 is designed to test whether there is a specific threshold for DIF, i.e., a point at which the effect of DIF changes significantly. The test for a single threshold shows that there is a single threshold effect for DIF and this effect is significant at the 10% level. This means that DIF may have a different effect on economic or business activity at a particular level. The results of the double-threshold test are not significant enough, which means that we do not have enough evidence to support the existence of two different threshold points that make a significant change in the effect of DIF.

Figure 2 shows the graph of the threshold regression. From the image, we can observe the following points: first, the likelihood ratio curve experiences a significant peak at a Gamma of about 0.8, which means that this point may be a significant threshold, i.e., when the DIF reaches this value, its impact may change significantly. This is consistent with the value of 0.7916 mentioned in the previous tabular data. Second, the green horizontal line indicates the significance level, e.g. 10%. Only when the likelihood ratio curve is above this line, we consider the Gamma value at that point to be significant. From the graph, the portion of the Gamma value of about 0.8 exceeds this line, further confirming its significance. Third, the apparent V-shaped structure in the figure indicates a significant change in the model fit near a Gamma of 0.8. The smooth portion on the left side indicates that before this threshold, increasing Gamma values have a

small effect on the model fit. However, when this threshold is exceeded, each unit change in the Gamma value significantly affects the model fit. In summary, this figure provides us with visual evidence that the effect of DIF changes significantly around a particular Gamma value (e.g., 0.8). This is consistent with previous regression results and further supports the idea that there is a significant threshold effect for DIF.

Table 8 shows the results of the DIF threshold regression, the threshold value of DIF is 0.7916, when $DIF \leq 0.7916$, its effect on the dependent variable is insignificant with a coefficient of -0.0086, a t-statistic of -0.08 and a p-value of 0.935. however, when $DIF \geq 0.7916$, it has a significant positive effect on the dependent variable which is close to significance at the 10% significance level with a The coefficient is 0.3152, the t-statistic is 1.92 and the p-value is 0.058. This may imply that simply having a certain level of DIF is not enough to produce significant benefits, but when it reaches a certain level, its advantages and benefits become apparent. The positive and significant coefficient of Top10 implies that an increase in the percentage of ownership of the major shareholders may increase the impact of DIF. This may be due to the fact that the increased decision-making power of major shareholders makes firms more likely to adopt or utilize DIF. Many other control variables, such as firm size (Size), debt level (Lev), and return on assets (ROA), are statistically insignificant, which implies that these variables may not be the main drivers of the DIF effect. Taken together, these

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results emphasize the role of DIF in firms and economic activities and reveal a certain critical level at which DIF has a significant impact. It also reminds us that not all firm

characteristics are associated with DIF benefits. The benefits of DIF may be more significant in certain contexts, such as when the shareholding of major shareholders is high.

Table 7 DIF threshold effect test results

Threshold	F	P	Number of BS	threshold value		
				1%	5%	10%
Single	11.77	0.0700	300	20.5313	14.8422	10.4552
Double	8.11	0.2000	300	20.0361	13.4173	10.4175

Table 8 Regressions and Tests for DIF Threshold

VARIABLES	Coef.	Std.Err	t	P> t
<i>Size</i>	0.0057	0.022	0.26	0.799
<i>Lev</i>	0.0010	0.130	0.01	0.994
<i>ROA</i>	-0.1019	0.304	-0.33	0.739
<i>Growth</i>	0.0039	0.022	0.18	0.858
<i>Top10</i>	0.3411**	0.164	2.08	0.041
<i>TobinQ</i>	-0.0011	0.010	-0.11	0.914
<i>SOE</i>	0.0501	0.031	1.63	0.107
<i>Big4</i>	-0.0382	0.113	-0.34	0.736
<i>DIF (DIF ≤ 0.7916)</i>	-0.0086	0.105	-0.08	0.935
<i>DIF (DIF ≥ 0.7916)</i>	0.3152*	0.164	1.92	0.058
<i>cons</i>	-0.2304	0.470	-0.49	0.625

Figure 2 DIF threshold regression graph

5.3 Threshold effect of TOP10

Table 9 aims to test whether there is a specific threshold for TOP10, i.e., a point at which the effect of TOP10 changes significantly. The test for a single threshold shows that there is a single threshold effect for TOP10 and this effect is significant at the 10% level. This means that the TOP10 may have a different effect on economic or business activity at a particular level. The results of the double-threshold test are not significant enough, which means that we do not have enough evidence to support the existence of two different threshold points that make a significant change in the effect of the TOP10.

Figure 3 shows the graph of the TOP10 threshold regression. As can be seen from the graph, the LR statistic reaches its minimum value when the gamma value is around 0.3681, which indicates that this point is the optimal threshold point and matches the description provided earlier. The green horizontal line in the figure indicates a certain threshold value of the LR statistic. The two points that cross this line then indicate the 95% confidence interval. We can see from the figure that the confidence interval is roughly between 0.35 and 0.38. This means that we can say with 95% confidence that the threshold is within this interval.

Table 10 shows the results of the threshold regressions and tests for the proportion of the top 10 largest shareholders (Top10). Here, we see a clear threshold effect which provides interesting insights about the impact of corporate governance and shareholder structure on firm decisions and performance. When the value of Top10 is less than or equal to 0.3681, i.e., the top 10 largest shareholders have a shareholding of less than or equal to 36.81%, it has a coefficient of 0.6600, which

is significant at the 5% level of significance. From an economic point of view, this could mean that when the top 10 shareholders have a lower percentage of ownership, they are more likely to keep a close eye on the company's operations and decision-making, and thus have a positive impact on the company. This is consistent with the "monitoring effect" in economics, whereby shareholders, as owners of a company, exert pressure on management to ensure that their behavior is consistent with the best interests of shareholders. As a result, for every 1% increase in shareholding, some of the company's performance metrics are likely to increase by about 0.6600 units. On the contrary, when the value of Top10 is higher than 0.3681, its coefficient significantly decreases to 0.0163 and is no longer statistically significant. This may imply that after a certain point in the concentration of shareholders' holdings, its incremental positive impact on the firm gradually diminishes. This can be interpreted as a "concentration effect". When minority shareholders hold too many shares in a company, they may be more likely to exert undue influence on corporate decisions that may not be entirely in the best interest of all shareholders. This may result in corporate management's behavior being inconsistent with the best interests of the overall shareholder group. Taken together, these findings highlight an equilibrium where the concentration of shareholder holdings should be at a moderate level to ensure effective corporate oversight while avoiding excessive concentration of power. Moreover, this highlights the importance of corporate governance mechanisms in maintaining this equilibrium by ensuring that the interests of shareholders are properly protected while encouraging management to create value for all shareholders.

Table 9 Threshold effect test results for the top 10 shareholders' ratios

Threshold	F	P	Number of BS	threshold value		
				1%	5%	10%
Single	13.51	0.0900	300	21.3264	16.6213	12.9111
Double	6.95	0.3133	300	19.7325	13.6813	11.3366

Table 10 Regressions and Tests for the Proportion of Top 10 Shareholders

VARIABLES	Coef.	Std.Err	t	P> t
<i>Size</i>	0.0337	0.022	1.56	0.122
<i>Lev</i>	0.0076	0.129	0.06	0.953
<i>ROA</i>	-0.0157	0.305	-0.05	0.959
<i>Growth</i>	-0.0044	0.021	-0.20	0.839

<i>Top10</i>	0.3972**	0.165	2.41	0.018
<i>TobinQ</i>	-0.0082	0.010	-0.80	0.428
<i>SOE</i>	0.0670*	0.034	1.95	0.055
<i>Big4</i>	0.0022	0.113	0.02	0.984
<i>Top10 (Top10≤0.3681)</i>	0.6600**	0.291	2.27	0.026
<i>Top10 (Top10≥0.3681)</i>	0.0163	0.116	0.14	0.889
<i>cons</i>	-0.8797*	0.467	-1.88	0.063

Figure 3 TOP10 threshold regression graph

6. CONCLUSIONS, RECOMMENDATIONS AND SHORTCOMINGS

6.1 Conclusions of the study

This paper focuses on the data of Chinese A-share listed companies in Shanghai and Shenzhen during the period from 2011 to 2020, and empirically analyzes how GDR affects the green technology innovation of firms in resource-based cities. This time period is chosen to capture the latest trends of the Chinese government's digital transformation and its potential impact on firms' innovation activities in the last decade. Our main findings can be summarized as follows:(1) GDR clearly provides a strong impetus to green technology innovation of resource-based city firms. More specifically, this effect is particularly evident in China's central regions and third-tier cities. This may be due to the fact that these regions have been given more opportunities in GDR or their innovation potential

has been better released after being driven by the policy. (2) After exploring the mechanism in depth, we find that GDR can optimize the allocation of land resources, thus creating a more conducive environment for green technological innovations of firms in resource-based cities. This implies that digital reform not only directly promotes technological innovation, but also provides enterprises with more efficient and rational resource allocation. (3) We further observe that there is a nonlinear relationship between DIF and TOP10 and the effect of GDR on FGI. The specific threshold analysis shows that when DIF does not exceed 0.7916, GDR does not have a significant role in promoting FGI in resource-based cities. However, when DIF exceeds 0.7916, its driving effect becomes significant. Similarly, when Top10 does not exceed 0.3681, the correlation between GDR and FGI is not strong; however, when the Top10 value exceeds this threshold, a

significant positive correlation is shown between the two.

6.2 Policy recommendations

Based on the findings of the previous study, the following targeted recommendations are made from the government, society and business perspectives: (1) Government perspective: first, strengthen the digitization process. Given the significant contribution of GDR to FGI in resource-based cities, the government should further optimize and accelerate the digitization process, especially in the central region and third-tier cities, in order to maximize the use of its potential benefits. Second, improve land resource allocation. The government should further optimize land resource allocation through digital technology, such as establishing a comprehensive land use database and providing real-time land use transparency to ensure efficient and sustainable use of land resources. Finally, optimize the DIF policy. After DIF reaches a certain threshold, the impact of DIF on green technology innovation is more significant, and the government should encourage the development of DIF, such as providing corresponding policy support and simplifying the registration and operation process of DIF. (2) Social perspective: First, improve digital awareness. All sectors of society, especially residents and enterprises in central and third-tier cities, should further raise awareness of GDR and understand its positive impact on FGI. Second, strengthen green technology education and training. Educational institutions and training centers should add courses and training programs on green technology and digitalization to encourage more people to understand and participate in innovative activities in this field. (3) Business perspective: First, actively embrace digital reform. Enterprises in resource cities should take the initiative to participate in the government's digital reform process and utilize the digital resources and platforms provided by the government for green technology innovation. Second, increase R&D investment. After TOP10 reaches a certain threshold, the driving effect of GDR on FGI becomes more obvious, and enterprises should further increase R&D investment, especially in DIF and other high-tech fields. Third, strengthen cooperation and communication. Enterprises in resource cities should strengthen cooperation and communication with the government, social organizations, research institutions, etc., to jointly promote the development of green technology innovation.

6.3. Insufficient research

From a research perspective, although this paper empirically explores the impact of GDR on FGI in resource-based cities, it is deficient in theory construction, interdisciplinary integration, and spatial heterogeneity. Especially in terms of micro-mechanisms and dynamic feedbacks, the paper may have failed to adequately capture the deep interactions between digital reforms and green technological innovations. In addition, the study may not have adequately considered the roles of other key stakeholders such as non-governmental organizations, research institutions, and consumers, as well as the differential impacts of policies, cultures, and infrastructures on green innovation in different regions. Therefore, more in-depth, multifaceted and integrated research perspectives remain the direction for future research.

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